

Atomic Layer Deposition - an Enabling and Critical Thin Film Technology

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Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) is the most advanced thin film deposition technique that offers sub-nanometer precision. Originally invented almost half a century ago, and hereto neglected, ALD was brought up to forefront due to shrinking dimensions in chip manufacturing. ALD is a cyclic process and it is based on the principle of chemisorption which is self-limiting in nature. In an ALD process, substrate surface and gaseous chemical precursor interaction is of utmost importance. The substrate surface must have receptor chemical groups on it on to which the incoming gaseous precursor groups can lock on to like a lock and key. A typical ALD cycle comprises four pulses that are repeated to build the desired film thickness as shown in Fig. 1 below.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of a cyclic ALD process. P is an inert gas pulse that drives away excess (physio-sorbed) or loosely attached precursor molecules from the surface thus forming a chemisorbed monolayer. This is the basis of an ALD reaction.

ALD offers extremely critical advantages unmatched by any other process at quite low cost: (a) precise, digital control of thin film thickness (b) large area deposition (c) fully conformal deposition over complex shapes and geometries at deep sub-micron level (d) very low defect and pinhole density (e) superior adhesion and (f) variety of materials – semiconductors, insulators, and metals. Thin film materials and their proven ALD processes are summarized by Suntola (ref. 1). Examples of thin film materials deposited by ALD are numerous. Among those: Si, GaAs, GaN, InGaN, ZnS/ZnSe, SiO_2 , AlN, Al_2O_3 , Cu, Ta, W, WN_x , TaN, TiN, TiO_2 and so on for fabrication of advanced silicon and optoelectronic devices, fuel cells, catalysts, flat panel displays.

The ALD process does not demand uniform spread of gaseous precursor nor does it require precise temperature uniformity of the substrate surface. An ALD chamber design is thus rather simple. However, this fact combined with the self-limiting nature of chemical process leads to ALD lower deposition rate ~ 1 nm/min. To remedy the situation, a novel ALD/CVD hybrid reactor design is devised as shown in Fig. 2 (ref. 2).

Surface coverage, $t = 50$ ms

Surface coverage, $t = 500$ ms

Fig. 2: Results of real-time computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation of the novel hybrid ALD/CVD reactor. Substrate $T = 500$ deg., at 60 rpm, 50 and sccm He flow.

Fig. 3 (left) shows pictorial view of an ALD/CVD system developed by Atomic Precision with a manual wafer loading mechanism to deposit GaN thin films at low temperatures (below 500 °C) by employing $N_2 + H_2$ gaseous mixture in a linear pulsed microwave plasma (refer to Fig. 1, $By_2 = NH_x$ and $Ax_2 = GaCl_3$) to deposit GaN thin films for LED device fabrication. (ref. 3)

An advanced ALD reactor design concept called Turbo-ALD is shown schematically in Fig. 4 which can be useful to deposit large area (m^2) thin films on flexible substrates at 15 – 20 x speed than current systems (ref. 4)

Fig. 4: Schematic of a Turbo-ALD reactor configuration.

References:

1. T. Suntola in Handbook of Crystal Growth 3, Part B, "Crystal Growth and Epitaxy", Ch. 14, D. T. J. Hurle (ed.), Elsevier, New York (1994)
2. Prasad N. Gadgil, US Patent No. 6,812,157.
3. Atomic Precision, NSF SBIR Phase – II Final Report No. 0750076, October 2014.
4. Prasad N. Gadgil, unpublished data, 2014.